

REQUIREMENTS TO THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE SPHERE OF CULTURAL AND AESTHETIC EDUCATION IN THE AREAS OF FINE ARTS, DESIGN, AND ARCHITECTURE

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the development of an educational environment for cultural and aesthetic education in the basic education system in the areas of fine arts, design, and architecture. The author examines a comprehensive approach to the educational process, the goals and objectives of which are focused on the educational environment, education, and training of students in cultural and aesthetic education in the above areas and help formulate requirements for the educational environment.

Currently, the cultural sphere is undergoing constant change, and spiritual and moral values are unstable. The current cultural and aesthetic situation is characterized as one of global spiritual and moral disharmony. In the context of a massive information flow, especially low-quality visual media, the human ability to understand the spiritual and material components of objects is limited. Particular attention is required to raising the level of cultural and aesthetic education of the population. Therefore, cultural and aesthetic training and education are crucial areas of education. This will significantly contribute to the restoration of spiritual and moral harmony.

Cultural and aesthetic education encompasses a wide variety of areas, each distinct in their specific processes of meaning-making, form-formation, value orientations, and goal settings. One such area is artistic and aesthetic education, through which individuals not only become familiar with aesthetic values through works of artistic culture but also develop their aesthetic and creative experience, artistic taste and intuition, and artistic competence [1].

The challenges of cultural and aesthetic education lie in the need for basic artistic, architectural, and design education, as well as cultural and aesthetic development and the development of students' abilities. The foundation of cultural and aesthetic values is laid during preschool and school years. Cultural and aesthetic education will enable children to see and understand the beauty of the surrounding world, cultivate a culture of feelings, develop artistic and aesthetic taste, enhance work and creative activity, and understand folk cultural traditions.

One of the main dangers is the intellectual crisis of national identity and the complete inadequacy of our understanding of the phenomenon of culture itself and its social role in maintaining social stability. Culture, above all, is the social solidarity of people, the sum total of the historical experience of collective existence, and masterpieces of spirit and creativity. The

development and popularization of cultural sciences based on knowledge of the technologies of design, planning, and management of such processes is essential for society. Therefore, cultural and aesthetic education is one of the most important areas of basic education [2].

Cultural and aesthetic activities expand the material and spiritual environment of society. Timely cultural and aesthetic education in the process of personal development requires a comprehensive approach. V. A. Kalashnikova identifies a "fundamental stage" that is linked to the overall development of a child's aesthetic culture, which indicates the need to introduce adjustments into the educational process [3].

Cultural and aesthetic education is the foundation of fine art, design, and architecture, encompassing the interconnectedness between material and artistic culture and the spiritual content of projects. The principle of combining familiar and unconventional elements in the aesthetic organization of the environment presupposes the comprehension of the aesthetic cognition of the unique language of art [4].

The works of E. V. Savelov, V. A. Kalashnikova and others are devoted to the study of issues of cultural and aesthetic education, however, the requirements imposed on the educational environment have not been studied.

Currently, there are no specialized learning spaces or environments for effective professional training of students; only adaptable spaces exist. Learning spaces do not meet the necessary requirements, lacking a comfortable environment for learning and teaching, storage, etc. Learning spaces must have design potential, versatility, and the ability to be transformed. A key aspect is a multifunctional, comfortable environment that does not distract from classes and has all the necessary areas for group and independent study, communication, and relaxation. Lighting, color, and specialized equipment are also essential. The design concept of spaces for cultural and aesthetic education addresses a number of issues: the ability to engage and engage in the learning process; development of initiative; and assistance and interaction with students and teachers. The key criteria for creating an educational environment include: open audio-visual spaces; a multifunctional environment; privacy and comfort; and others. It is essential to create an appropriate environment for systematic, practice-oriented study of disciplines, which will allow students to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills. The choice of artistic techniques and technological means will enable the embodiment of the concept in the material. Cultural and aesthetic education is essential for attaining a properly organized environment and educational process. It is essential to create a learning environment that includes a structure aimed at achieving the primary outcome. The structure of the environmental space for cultural and aesthetic education includes activities (basic education, aesthetic and cultural development, development of abilities, etc.), information (standards of basic general education, the basic general education program, original programs, teaching and methodological kits, didactic handouts, multimedia educational programs, electronic libraries, etc.), and material equipment (specialized space, specialized classroom furniture, teaching and practical equipment, technical teaching aids, models and natural resources, etc.) that are consistent with innovative activities. Additional original curricula that possess general cultural and aesthetic values should also be developed. Therefore, there is a need to develop a design concept for environmental spaces for cultural and aesthetic education based on an innovative educational subject-spatial environment, including material and information equipment, and creative activities.

Design education, fine arts, and architectural education are directly linked to cultural and aesthetic education, which is essential for preserving the integrity of the individual and society. The design and implementation of specialized learning environments and programs is essential. Cultural and aesthetic education and the implementation of modern design projects for educational environments are among the most important areas of development and education. Introducing students to cultural and aesthetic values, both material and spiritual, is essential.

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